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Visual Astronomy Display: January 2015

Katie Frey

Updated on August 24, 2022

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Visual Astronomy Display for January 2015

Happy New Year!

Highlights...

- This year, the **Hubble Space Telescope celebrates 25 years** of transforming our view of the universe;
- A color image of stars from the globular star cluster Omega Centauri are sorted by **brightness and color to construct a Hertzsprung-Russel diagram**, an innovative and easy to understand way to show a graph used by astronomers to trace stellar evolution;
- MinutePhysics gives us an **astronomically correct version of Twinkle Twinkle Little Star**;
- Voyager I has experienced **three “tsunami waves,” resulting from coronal mass ejections** from the Sun, as it travels through interstellar space, and;
- AsapSCIENCE describes what it would take for people to begin **living on the Red Planet**.

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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